

Role of MRI in Assessment of Pituitary Lesions: A Case Series of Pituitary Masses

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ABSTRACT

Pituitary masses are relatively common among general population with incidence varying from 10-12 percent. Most of these lesions are small, even microscopic; consequently, most patients are asymptomatic. Unnecessary surgery should be avoided by improving understanding of disease and its natural history. To diagnose intracranial pathology, we have conducted an observational case series of patients referred to the Department of Radiodiagnosis PCMS and RC for MRI brain. Patients with pituitary masses were identified with pituitary enlargement nearby or approaching the sellar region on MR imaging.

The first patient presented with craniopharyngioma of adamantinomatous type. The second patient was diagnosed with pituitary macro adenoma, while third patient was diagnosed after observing small nodule in anterior lobe of pituitary in left half suggestive of micro adenoma. The fourth patient likely had cystic / necrotic transformation of previous macro adenoma with haemorrhage. The fifth patient's MRI Brain reveals empty sella.

Dynamic contrast enhanced imaging played a crucial role in accurate localization of hormone secreting microadenomas and other pituitary lesions. MRI precisely assessed the invasion of cavernous sinus by macroadenomas on contrast enhanced imaging. MRI is undoubtedly an indispensable tool to evaluate hypothalamic-pituitary related endocrine disease.

MRI not only provides diagnosis, but also helps to plan surgical strategies due to its ability to provide multiplanar details of anatomical relationship of the gland to surrounding structures. It is also a method of choice for follow-up imaging in order to determine the response to conservative therapy as well as to identify remnant lesions/recurrence in postoperative situations. A comprehensive hormonal, radiological and even occasionally ophthalmological examination should be done for patients suspicious of developing pituitary masses. This is best done by a specialized multidisciplinary approach with a preference for the treatment of underlying conditions and constant monitoring for surgery.

KEY WORDS: craniopharyngioma, dynamic MRI, empty sella, microadenoma, pituitary macroadenoma

INTRODUCTION:

The sella is one of the most complex anatomical region in the brain. It encompasses the bony sella turcica and pituitary gland plus all the normal structures that surround it. Virtually any of these can give rise to pathology that ranges from incidental and innocuous to serious, potentially life-threatening disease. Sellar or suprasellar regions are most common site for pituitary tumors. The prevalence of clinically apparent pituitary lesions is estimated to comprise approximately 10% to 12% of all

intracranial lesions with an annual incidence of 0.2 to 2.8 cases per 100,000 persons^[1,2], while incidental pituitary tumors are detected in approximately 11% of individuals at autopsy. It is noted that craniopharyngiomas are responsible for 1 to 4 percent of all primary intracranial neoplasms and appear at a frequency of 1.3 per million years per human^[3]. Most pituitary tumors are considered to be benign adenomas, although around 0.5 percent of pituitary tumors have been reported as pituitary carcinoma^[4]. In past decades, pituitary gland imaging has acquired significant attention and progressed rapidly. Indirect methods of detecting pituitary gland dysfunction by evaluation of sella turcica on skull radiographic films and tomography are being replaced by direct visualisation of the gland with CT and MRI[5,6]. The revolutionary advance that have occurred in imaging modalities of the brain provide extensive details of anatomical relationship and have led to an increased

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detection rate of pituitary lesions. The advent of dynamic contrast MR imaging has been helpful for diagnosis and treatment of pituitary lesions. MRI also helps to know nature, extent, operability of tumour and surgical approach.

As suggested by clinical signs and symptoms, appropriate imaging of the hypothalamic-pituitary axis is based on specific endocrine testing. Thin-section (2-3 mm) multiplanar MR with a small field of view obtained before and after contrast administration, including dynamic as well as static sequences, is the best imaging procedure for hypothalamic-pituitary axis abnormalities. CTA, MRA, DSA, and petrosal sinus sampling are supplemental techniques in selected cases. Contrast-enhanced CT occasionally facilitates diagnosis of neuroendocrine abnormalities but is less sensitive than MR. Bone CT may be helpful in depicting the extent of bony involvement with invasive adenomas or differentiating lesions that arise in the basisphenoid.

MRI is the primary imaging method for the study and characterization of normal anatomy and pathological process in this region^[5,6,7]. We have here in the radiologic finding of pituitary lesions of the cases which were diagnosed in the Radiodiagnosis Department of People's College Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhopal and to assess the capability of MRI in diagnosis of pituitary lesions.

CASE PRESENTATION: MRI IMAGING

Case 1:-

A 7 years old child came to medicine OPD with the complaints of headache on/off since last 1 month and visual disturbance for last 3 weeks. Patient was referred to the department of radiodiagnosis for MRI brain to diagnose any intracranial pathology.

MRI brain finding reveals a well-defined solid-cystic heterogeneous mass lesion measuring (2.2x2.5x4.0 cm) seen in supra sellar region (Figure 1A). The solid portion of mass seen on pituitary gland measures of size 1.2 cm x1.06 cm. On T1WI, it appeared heterogeneously iso to hypo intense and on T2WI/FLAIR picture, intermediate to hyper intense (Figure 1B) with heterogenous post contrast enhancement.

Opinion: MRI study of brain reveals a well-defined predominantly cystic mass lesion in suprasellar region showing areas of calcification and mild heterogeneous post contrast enhancement. Above imaging features are suggestive of craniopharyngioma (adamantinomatous type).

(1A)

(1B)

Figure 1A & 1B : MRI pre and post contrast images of the Pituitary mass, craniopharyngioma discussed in Case 1.

Case 2:-

A 17 year old male, with complaints of inability to gain height with increasing age since last 5 years and markedly decreased vision since last 6 weeks.

MRI brain revealed a large well defined avidly enhancing 'figure of 8' appearance soft tissue mass in pituitary fossa causing widening of the sella with the suprasellar and right parasellar extension (Figure 2A). There were also few non enhancing areas noted within the mass with multiple small areas of blooming in GRE suggestive of focal haemorrhages (Figure 2B). It appears that mass is encasing internal carotid artery at its bifurcation with posterior communicating artery and causing invasion of right cavernous sinus (Figure 2C & 2D). Optic chiasma is markedly compressed and displaced postero-superiorly, predominantly left side. In superior extension mass is extending up to 3rd ventricle with mild indentation with no evidence of hydrocephalous at the time.

Opinion: A large 'figure of 8' appearing avidly enhancing sellar mass with suprasellar and right parasellar extension. The findings are in favour of pituitary macro adenoma.

2 A

2 B

Figure 2 A : MR coronal FLAIR images showing Pituitary mass lesion discussed in Case 2.

Figure 2 B : MRI axial GRE images of the Brain showing pituitary lesion discussed in Case 2.

2 C

2 D

Figure 2 C & D : MRI coronal and axial T2WI images of the Brain showing pituitary lesion discussed in Case 2.

Case 3:-

A 31 year old female with the complaints of headache, dizziness, blurred vision since one month on and off was referred to Department of Radiodiagnosis for MRI brain to rule out any intracranial pathology.

MRI findings of pituitary gland show a small nodule of size 5x4 mm in left half of anterior lobe (Figure 3A & 3B).

Opinion: A small nodule is noted in anterior lobe of pituitary in left half suggestive of micro adenoma. Rest of the brain is normal in morphology and signal intensity.

Case 4:-

A male 32 year old, with the complaints of fatigue, headache and blurred vision since 2 month on and off was referred to Department of Radiodiagnosis

3 A

3 B

Figure 3A & 3B: MR saggital and coronal images of the Brain showing pituitary microadenoma as discussed in Case 3.

4 A

4 B

Figure 4A & 4B : MR Saggital and coronal images of the Brain shows pituitary mass lesion discussed in Case 4.

for MRI brain to diagnose any intracranial pathology.

MRI findings shows that sella was widened. Predominantly cystic lesion of size 2.5 x 2.4 x 1.8 cm. (CC x TR x AP) was seen in sella with mural nodule of 6x5 mm size (Figure 4A). The lesion was indenting left half of optic chiasma. No parasellar extension was seen and pituitary stalk was deviated towards left side (Figure 4B).

MR imaging appearance favours possibility of cystic/necrotic transformation of previous macro adenoma with haemorrhage.

Case 5:-

A male patient of 22 years old, complaints of headache, dizziness and blurred vision since 3 month and learning disability. MRI brain finding reveals

Figure 5A & 5B: MRI coronal T2WI and sagittal flair images of the Brain showing empty sella as discussed in Case 5.

Empty sella measuring 11x17x10mm. (Figure 5A & 5B)

Opinion: MRI Brain with pituitary reveals empty sella. Tortuous optic nerves with prominent peri-optic nerve sheath.

DISCUSSION:

Pituitary imaging is essential tool in order to confirm the diagnosis and for differential of other sellar lesions. An empty sella (ES) is an arachnoid-lined, CSF-filled protrusion that extends from suprasellar cistern to the sella turcica through diaphragm sellae. ES is rarely completely 'empty'; a small remnant of flattened pituitary gland is almost always present at the bottom of the bony sella, even if it is in apparent on imaging studies. Therefore, the term 'partially empty sella' is anatomically more accurate. Imaging observations of empty sella suggest intrasellar CSF with flat thin pituitary gland remnant in the sellar floor. On MR Findings, the intrasellar fluid behaves exactly like CSF on T1- and T2WI and suppresses completely on FLAIR. DWI shows no diffusion restriction.

Craniopharyngioma (CP) is a benign, often partly cystic sellar/suprasellar mass that probably arises from epithelial remnants of Rathke pouch. Clinically it occurs in > 50% of pediatric suprasellar neoplasms, also found equally in adults and have peak in 5-15 years and 40-55 years in

children and adults respectively. Papillary type is much more common in adults. Slow growth and recurrence are common with rare malignant transformation. MRI imaging shows variable signal on T1WI and hyperintense on T2/FLAIR with Enhancement (nodular or rim). MRS shows large lipid-lactate peak^[8].

Pituitary adenomas consist of secretory cells that secrete pituitary hormones. Microadenomas are tumors of size upto 10 mm in diameter, while masses more than 10 mm are considered as macroadenomas. On MRI, it is isointense with cortex and heterogeneous signal intensity is common due to cystic and haemorrhagic changes of adenoma. Heterogeneous enhancement of microadenomas seen is with dynamic T1 C+. Historically, before the advent of CT scan or MRI, the pituitary was imaged with lateral skull x-rays to detect remodelling of the pituitary fossa. However, the radiographic size of sella is not a sensitive predictor of pituitary gland abnormality. Thus the plain radiographs were replaced by CT imaging. Although CT was able to detect up to 80-90% of microadenomas (between 8-10 mm in size) and other lesions while radiologists faced a difficulty in identifying smaller nodules^[9].

Hence, CT is replaced by Magnetic Resonance Imaging which is now the modality of choice in the imaging of pituitary lesions due to its superior soft tissue contrast, multiplanar imaging and minimum ionizing radiation. In addition, MRI also

provides valuable knowledge about the anatomy of the gland with neighbouring structures and helps in decision to plan surgery^[10,11].

The optimum enhancement in healthy pituitary tissue and microadenomas is achieved in dynamic imaging within 30-60 seconds after IV bolus injection of contrast medium, whereas most microadenomas tend to be relatively non-enhancing lesions within an intensely enhancing pituitary gland. Dynamic MRI is also useful for residual/recurrent tumour differentiation.

The information provided by MRI in cases of pituitary lesion is highly useful for physician treatment and surgeon for planning of treatment and operability. In most cases, the tumours remain cytologically benign inspite of their invasive behaviour since the intracavernous cranial nerves occupy the lateral position in the sinus and clinical signs of cavernous sinus invasion occurs late^[12]. It is crucial to analyze the encroachment of the cavernous sinus, and at this stage complete surgical removal of the tumor is difficult, so in these cases, radiation therapy is recommended. On MR imaging, the most reliable sign of cavernous sinus invasion is tumour encasing the carotid artery.

Majority of the macroadenomas appear isointense on T1WI and T2WI and show homogenous early enhancement on post contrast study. Those showing cystic degeneration / necrosis are seen to have hyperintense signal intensity on T2WI, with a non-enhancing area within, on post contrast images. Soft adenoma (easy to operate) appears hyperintense in diffusion weighted images with low ADC value.

Hard adenoma (difficult to operate by Endoscopic Trans-sphenoidal technique) appears hypointense on DWI and shows high ADC values^[13]. In addition, DWI also helps in early detection of pituitary apoplexy (Haemorrhage/infarction). Thus, DWI should be a part of MRI study for evaluation of pituitary adenoma prior to surgery.

Recent advances in MRI evaluation of pituitary adenoma include Magnetization Transfer (MT) imaging, MR spectroscopy and Intraoperative MRI (IMRI). MT images also help in post-operative assessment of residual tumour (high signal on MT images) when findings are negative on routine MRI sequences^[14]. Primary role of MR spectroscopy is to differentiate various types of pituitary lesion. On MR spectroscopy pituitary adenoma may show a choline peak^[15]. Use of IMRI during endoscopic pituitary surgery has proven to be very useful in localizing and complete resection of invasive pituitary adenoma^[16].

CONCLUSION:

MRI provides excellent choice for the diagnosis of hypothalamic-pituitary-related endocrine diseases/disorders. This not only assists in the diagnosis of all these lesions but also provides valuable information of anatomical relationship of the pituitary gland to the surrounding tissues. MRI also serves as a guide for surgical approach.

MRI is also an important method for assessing patient's treatment conservatively and post-operatively, as well as for evaluating sensitivity to therapy. We assume that an experienced multidisciplinary team is ideally suitable for pituitary masses to be characterized and monitored. Immediate emergency surgery should be discouraged, giving priority to a detailed investigation and close supervision of the causative factors of pituitary lesions.

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